

What's been causing changes in UK insect populations?

Insects are under pressure from various factors, including intensified land use, climate change, pollution, and the emergence of new pests and diseases. Although these general threats have been known about for some time there is little robust evidence about the details of what is really happening.

The UK is unmatched in terms of the amount of data on where various insect species have been observed. This includes vast sets of species observations (records that we refer to as "insect occupancy" data) built up through the expertise of committed volunteers on national recording schemes such as the British Dragonfly Society and the Bees Wasps and Ants Recording Society.

Amateur naturalists have been monitoring insects since the 18th century. The establishment of the Royal Entomological Society in 1833 helped lead to more organized recording and sharing of insect data.

The new improved weather radar at the Met Office enable us to count a billion movements of air-borne insects over vast areas — twenty-four seven.

- The UK has an unmatched collection of data that tracks where different species of insect are found, and how their numbers are changing over time. This huge dataset is complex, making it difficult to analyse.
- Advances in computer technology and analytical methods mean that we can now discover the secrets held within these data and begin to understand what is happening to our insects.
- The advanced analysis undertaken in the DRUID (Drivers & Repercussions of UK Insect Declines) project has revealed a complex picture with winners and losers across different insect groups.
- We now have strong evidence that climate change, urban development, and changes in farmed and natural landscapes are affecting the composition of Britain's insect communities.

Data collected by volunteer networks using more standardised, repeated monitoring surveys are available from the Rothamsted Insect Survey, the UK Butterfly Monitoring Scheme and more recently the UK Pollinator Monitoring Scheme, amongst others. We now even have data on flying insect abundance derived from weather monitoring radar. Together these data sets form an amazing resource that allows us to understand what is happening to our insects and why.

Because of the vast quantity of insect records involved and the fact that they are collected by various people, at different times and in various weather conditions, there are some big statistical and computational challenges associated with how we analyse the data and interpret the results.

Our Approach We used powerful computers and the latest advances in statistics and machine learning methods to analyse the data. Changes in thousands of insect species were mapped and modelled across Great Britain.

Key Findings Our analyses show an overall decline in insect occupancy since 1970, but since 1990 overall trends appear to have been more stable. However, this picture hides the fact that there are both winners and losers.

Evidence shows that some groups of insects, like hoverflies and soldierflies, have declined, whereas others, such as dragonflies, have increased.

Insects are affected by a variety of factors in both positive and negative ways. Out of the factors we considered, this map shows what is most likely to be having a positive effect on insects in each location. For most places, it is the increase in average temperature, but increasing landscape diversity in some locations is also having beneficial effect.

Implications DRUID has provided new evidence that our changing environment is impacting insects. A warmer climate favours species which can fit in more than one generation per year, as they are more likely to successfully raise additional generations (e.g. the Duke of Burgundy butterfly). This raises concerns for species that only have one generation per year, or which have a very limited flight period (e.g. the stag beetle), as the changing climate does not help them in their competition for resources.

It also suggests possible risks for fast-reproducing species, as extra generations in a warmer environment might lead them into harmful situations where, for example, the extra generation isn't mature enough for overwintering when the cold weather comes. Climates aren't just getting warmer—they're becoming more unpredictable. So even if insects adapt to higher temperatures, they may experience a population crash when a colder year occurs.

This, as well as the reduced amount and variety of insect habitats across many of our landscapes and changing ecosystems, could have serious impacts on the diversity of insects Great Britain can support. Insects provide many benefits, such as pollinating our crops, cycling soil nutrients, and are a major source of food for many animals including birds, bats, amphibians, reptiles and fish. Without insects, ecosystems would collapse, food production would suffer, and biodiversity would decline drastically. We must continue to monitor and record insect species to understand how they are responding to changing environments.

There are also some small and effective things that we can do to support our insects. For example, our built areas need not be so hostile to insects, we can keep wild areas in our gardens, choose insect-friendly plants and reduce the use of garden chemicals. You can also get involved with observing and recording insects. For more information on how to get involved with recording and the scientific analysis that underpins this fact sheet visit our [website](#).

Insects support our planet, so let's support our insects!

